

Studies on the Continuous Phase in the Vicinity of Emulsion Droplets: Part II

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The creaming data for various oil-in-water emulsions with Na-oleate as emulsifying agent, prepared under identical conditions, were fitted in an exponential equation proposed by the authors in Part I of this series. The effects of emulsifier concentration and the nature of disperse phase were studied on the critical phase-volume ratio ϕ_c as determined graphically from the creaming constant λ and corresponding phase-volume ratio ϕ for each emulsion system. The ratio of the co-sphere radius r_c to the radius of the emulsified droplet r_d was determined from the ϕ_c values as well as from viscosity data for the systems studied.

A PREVIOUS paper in this series¹ described the determination of critical phase-volume ratio ϕ_c at which the co-sphere, resulting from the existence of a layer of considerable thickness of continuous phase surrounding the dispersed droplets, touch each other in an emulsion system. In the same continuation the present investigation deals with the determination of the values of ϕ_c and the ratio of the co-sphere radius r_c to the radius of the emulsified droplet r_d for a few other emulsion systems along with the effect of emulsifier concentration on them.

Experimental

Materials: Benzene, toluene, chlorobenzene and bromobenzene used as disperse phases and Na-oleate used as emulsifier were BDH (India) and BDH (England) products respectively. *O*-xylene, *m*-xylene and *p*-xylene as disperse phases were E. Merck (Germany) products while the continuous phase in each case was double distilled conductivity water.

Preparation of emulsions: Emulsions were prepared following the agent-in-water method².

Procedure: Different benzene-in-water, toluene-in-water, *o*-xylene-in-water, *m*-xylene-in-water, *p*-xylene-in-water, chlorobenzene-in-water and bromobenzene-in-water emulsions with varying phase-volume ratio ϕ and concentration C (g/100 ml emulsion) of Na-oleate as emulsifier were prepared and allowed to cream in graduated glass jars kept in water bath maintained at a temperature of $30^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$. The height of the separating cream L in cm with corresponding time t in sec. for all the emulsions creaming upwards were noted in the manner reported earlier¹.

For emulsions creaming downwards the height of the upper layer of emulsion L_0 and the height of the upper layer of the separating cream L_t from the bottom of the jar at different times were noted and the difference $L_0 - L_t$ was taken to be L at the corresponding time t . Further, the emulsion viscosities were determined at $30^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$ by Ostwald viscometer¹, while the density was measured by standard method using pycnometer¹.

Results and Discussion

The values of $\log L$ were plotted against $1/t$ in each case in order to test the validity of the following equation suggested earlier by the authors¹

$$L = L'e^{-\lambda t} \quad (1)$$

where L and t are as defined above and L' and λ are constants. The plots of $\log L$ versus $1/t$ for the systems having the density of disperse phase less than that of continuous phase were linear in each case and the λ values were determined from the corresponding slopes. This justifies the validity of equation (1) for those of the investigated systems where creaming occurs against gravity. However, in case of systems having density of the disperse phase greater than that of the continuous phase, the plot of $\log L$ versus $1/t$ was linear only when the emulsions were dilute. For emulsions with higher ϕ the deviation from linearity was appreciable. A typical plot of $\log L$ versus $1/t$ is shown in Figure 1 for such systems.

A close observation of these curves shows that for the systems with $\phi > 0.40$ and emulsifier concentration 1.0%, the larger number of points fall on a straight line after it bends. But the reverse is the case for these systems with emulsifier concentration 2.0%, whereas, the situation is in between when emulsifier concentration is 1.5%.

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It appears that for systems creaming downwards the deformation of droplets plays an important role by changing the value of L . The observed L is greater than the actual L which would have been measured in the absence of any deformation. Such droplet deformation is caused by the hydrostatic pressure of the separated continuous phase when

in the case of systems creaming downwards, were plotted against corresponding ϕ for each system and for every concentration of emulsifier studied.

An abrupt change in slope occurred in the plot of λ against ϕ at a particular value of $\phi = \phi_c$ for each system. While the initial portion of the curve was nearly linear in each case, the final portion did not always approximate linearity and the deviations were considerable in some cases. Apparently ϕ_c corresponded to the point where the curve represented by the initial portion of the data envelope intersected another curve representing the final portion of the data envelop. The point of intersection and consequently ϕ_c for each system studied was conveniently determined by plotting $\log \lambda$ versus $\log \phi$ which transformed the curves into straight lines. Figure 2 shows the plots of $\log \lambda$ versus $\log \phi$ for a typical system studied.

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log L$ against $1/t$ at $30^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$ for chlorobenzene/water emulsions stabilised by (A) 1% Na-oleate, (B) 1.5% Na-oleate and (C) 2% Na-oleate.

inter droplet distances get sufficiently shorter with the progress of creaming. If such systems have smaller ϕ the relative change in L due to deformation is small and thus unimportant. Consequently, the curves from $\log L$ versus $1/t$ plot are linear. But in the case of systems with larger ϕ , the relative change in L due to droplet deformation is prominent. This causes the deviation of $\log L$ versus $1/t$ curve from linearity. In order to calculate the value of λ unaffected by any deformation, straight line joining the data points corresponding to smaller t values only were taken into consideration because the inter droplet distances are larger during the initial stages of creaming and the chances of droplet deformation occurring are remote. The values of λ , as determined from the slope of the straight lines obtained from $\log L$ versus $1/t$ plot in the case of systems creaming upward and from the slope of extrapolated lines

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log \lambda$ against $\log \phi$ at $30^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$ for chlorobenzene/water emulsions stabilised by (A) 1% Na-oleate, (B) 1.5% Na-oleate and (C) 2% Na-oleate.

As pointed out by the authors in their earlier publication in this series¹, the plot of emulsion viscosity η against corresponding ϕ were linear in each case in the region $\phi_c > \phi > 0.20$ as well as in the region $\phi_c < \phi < 0.60$ with an abrupt change in slope at $\phi = \phi_c$.

The mean values of ϕ_c determined from creaming and viscosity data were used for calculating the ratio r_s/r_d by using the relation

$$\frac{r_s}{r_d} = \left(\frac{0.74}{\phi_c} \right)^{1/3} \quad (2)$$

where r_s is the radius of the co-sphere and r_d is the radius of the corresponding droplet.

The values of ϕ_c from creaming data as well as viscosity data along with the values of r_s/r_d for each system studied, with three different concentrations of the emulsifier used, are mentioned in Table 1.

A close scrutiny of the values of ϕ_c in Table 1 reveals that the increase in the concentration of the emulsifier from 1.0% to 1.5% and then to 2.0% decreases the value of ϕ_c and hence increases the ratio r_s/r_d according to equation (2), provided other parameters for an emulsion system are kept constant. Further, the change of disperse phase also changes the value of ϕ_c and consequently r_s/r_d . Earlier workers³⁻⁵, have also observed that the variation in emulsifier concentration as well as the change in the nature of disperse phase affects the value of Siblee's constant h which is considered to be a volume factor and can be compared with r_s/r_d .

The variations in r_s/r_d , or in other words ϕ_c , with emulsifier concentration is probably due to changed distribution of emulsifier in the disperse phase, continuous phase and at the droplet surface when the emulsifier concentration is changed. As the droplet surface accommodates emulsifier molecules giving rise to a surface layer only a few molecules thick, the emulsifier concentration in the surface layer may not change appreciably beyond a certain value of total emulsifier concentration. If the total emulsifier concentration is increased further, the additional emulsifier gets suitably distributed between the disperse as well as continuous phase and immobilises the disperse and continuous phase molecules by solvation or micellisation. Immobilisation of disperse phase molecules changes the viscosity of the internal phase which may not affect the behaviour of droplets if their diameter is small and the interfacial film is sufficiently rigid; but if it is not so, the effect is appreciable. On the other hand, the immobilisation of the continuous phase molecules changes the continuous phase viscosity and reduces the volume of free continuous phase. The net effect of increasing the emulsifier concentration within the range studied is thus expected to increase the value of r_s/r_d which has actually been observed as stated earlier.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF ϕ_c AND r_s/r_d FOR DIFFERENT EMULSION SYSTEMS AT VARYING EMULSIFIER CONCENTRATIONS

Temp. = $30^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$

Sl. no.	System	Creaming direction	C %	$\log \lambda - \log \phi$ curve	$\frac{\phi_c}{\eta - \phi}$ curve	Mean ϕ_c	r_s/r_d
1.	Benzene/Water	Upwards	1.0	0.430	0.430	0.430	1.1983
			1.5	0.407	0.393	0.400	1.2275
			2.0	0.372	0.380	0.376	1.2531
2.	Toluene/Water	Upwards	1.0	0.447	0.440	0.444	1.1856
			1.5	0.407	0.410	0.409	1.2185
			2.0	0.376	0.385	0.381	1.2477
3.	<i>o</i> -Xylene/Water	Upwards	1.0	0.452	0.450	0.451	1.1794
			1.5	0.412	0.418	0.415	1.2126
			2.0	0.380	0.385	0.383	1.2455
4.	<i>m</i> -Xylene/Water	Upwards	1.0	0.468	0.460	0.464	1.1682
			1.5	0.412	0.420	0.416	1.2116
			2.0	0.385	0.395	0.390	1.2379
5.	<i>p</i> -Xylene/Water	Upwards	1.0	0.380	0.390	0.385	1.2433
			1.5	0.369	0.360	0.365	1.2656
			2.0	0.359	0.357	0.358	1.2738
6.	Cl-benzene/Water	Downwards	1.0	0.398	0.398	0.398	1.2296
			1.5	0.380	0.375	0.378	1.2510
			2.0	0.380	0.367	0.374	1.2552
7.	Br-benzene/Water	Downwards	1.0	0.389	0.390	0.390	1.2379
			1.5	0.376	0.376	0.376	1.2531
			2.0	0.376	0.370	0.373	1.2565

If, however, the emulsifier concentration is kept constant and disperse phase is changed, then again the distribution of emulsifier between disperse phase, continuous phase as well as the droplet surface is altered due to change in the solubility of the emulsifier in the new disperse phase. This in turn causes a change in r_s/r_d which is obvious from the experimental data.

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